

Supplementary Material

1 BACKGROUND

AI tools for code suggestion. Tools such as GitHub Copilot and ChatGPT 5.2 are widely studied for their ability to generate code from natural language descriptions (Yetiştirilgen et al., 2023). Analyses of these tools often involve measuring security (Pearce et al., 2025), readability, and effectiveness in different scenarios (Mastropaolo et al., 2023). The increasing adoption of these tools motivates researchers to examine contextual factors such as language, prompt size, algorithmic complexity, and aspects of memorization (Yang et al., 2024), all of which can affect the precision of suggestions.

However, recent studies have also shown that these AIs can produce functional but insecure code (Pearce et al., 2025), or repeat verbal excerpts from publicly available repositories. This raises concerns about license violations and privacy (Yang et al., 2024). Furthermore, non-determinism of the model can hinder the replicability of experiments (Ouyang et al., 2022), suggesting the need for approaches that consider multiple submissions or different generation parameters.

In the context of the impact of different languages on language models, investigations on machine translation and linguistic bias show that language models can exhibit performance discrepancies depending on the language (Abid et al., 2021). Such discrepancies generally arise from differences in the availability of training data and the grammatical structures of languages (Nguyen and Nadi, 2022).

One particularly relevant study is that of (Koyanagi et al., 2024), which investigated the impact of different natural languages on the accuracy of code suggestions generated by GitHub Copilot. The study considered English, Japanese, and Chinese. The authors found that AI performance varied significantly depending on the prompt language: Japanese showed the best accuracy rate, English was intermediate, and Chinese produced the worst results. This linguistic bias was attributed to the availability of training data, as the AtCoder platform was originally problematic in English and Japanese but not in Chinese. This finding confirms that AI models can exhibit different be-

haviors depending on the language used, which affects the effectiveness and reliability of the suggestions provided.

In terms of empirical studies based on programming problems, the evaluation of AI models using programming challenge platforms is a well-established practice, as these platforms provide comprehensive test sets (Beecrowd, 2025). Empirical studies often use metrics such as the accuracy rate to measure how well the generated solution meets the requirements of each problem (Mastropaolo et al., 2023). Although there are studies that compare model performance on platforms such as LeetCode or AtCoder (Nguyen and Nadi, 2022; Koyanagi et al., 2024), research focusing specifically on Beecrowd remains limited, prompting a closer examination of this platform (Beecrowd, 2025).

About biases, security, and non-determinism in code generation models, in addition to language-related issues, the literature highlights several other challenges in using AI to generate code. Regarding security, (Pearce et al., 2025) showed that approximately 40% of the code generated by GitHub Copilot contained vulnerabilities. This raises questions about the extent to which language can affect the security characteristics of the code, as well as its quality and functional accuracy.

Another aspect concerns memorization: (Yang et al., 2024) demonstrated that code models can reproduce entire sections of their training data, exposing potential privacy, licensing, and security risks. Although this type of analysis is not the main focus of this study, the way in which the problem statement is worded (e.g. in different languages) may influence the likelihood of the model using standardized or memorized code.

Finally, (Ouyang et al., 2022) analyzed the non-determinism of ChatGPT, showing that multiple executions of the same prompt can generate structurally different code, even when the temperature is set to zero. In the present study, this factor led to the adoption of five submissions per problem and language to capture variations that could arise in different interactions with the model.

2 LIMITATIONS

While the results of this study are relevant to understanding ChatGPT 5.2's performance on the Beecrowd platform, they cannot be generalized to other challenge platforms or different programming environments. This is because the research was conducted in a very specific way, addressing only mathematical problems on a single platform. Beecrowd may present problem statement patterns, test formats, and question types that are not necessarily reproduced in other platforms such as Codeforces, AtCoder, or LeetCode. Furthermore, it is important to emphasize that problem categories with broader requirements or very distinct structures, such as Graphs, Data Structures, and Dynamic Programming, were not considered — areas that may demand greater model abstraction capabilities to handle more complex algorithms. In short, the scope of this study limits the extrapolation of the results to other competitive programming contexts and challenge platforms, highlighting the importance of further studies that encompass more diverse scenarios.

Another factor restricting the general applicability of the findings is the exclusive use of the Python language. ChatGPT 5.2 may produce different results in C++, Java, or other languages due to differences in syntax, semantics, and programming paradigms. These differences include memory management, exception handling, and the availability of native libraries to solve specific problems. Therefore, while it was appropriate to analyze the model's behavior in a widely used language, it is important to note that the results do not allow us to conclude how the AI would perform if the same set of problems were presented in languages with different characteristics.

Automatic translation of the statements into English and Spanish may have influenced the results to some extent. Despite using Google Translate and making occasional revisions to ensure coherence, some linguistic nuances may have been overlooked. Small translation errors or terminological inconsistencies can affect the clarity of the instructions provided to the model. In specific cases, this may result in AI making incorrect interpretations. Furthermore, even adequate translations can subtly modify the format or structure of certain sentences, thereby influencing how the LLM processes information and generates code. Therefore, although the study has striven to standardize this process, it is not possible to completely rule out the impact of any inaccuracies in translation.

Another point that deserves to be highlighted is the constant evolution of ChatGPT 5.2. The model

undergoes periodic updates that can modify its knowledge base and text generation logic. This means that research conducted at different times, even if attempting to replicate the same methodology, may produce different results. It cannot be stated with complete certainty that if the experiment were repeated months later, the same numbers would be observed. This dynamic nature of the model presents an additional challenge to the academic community, as it calls into question the reproducibility of experiments involving constantly improving AIs.

Furthermore, ChatGPT 5.2 is a non-deterministic model, meaning that the same prompt can generate different answers on different occasions, depending on the algorithms and probabilities that guide the choice of each subsequent token. For this reason, conducting five attempts per problem and per language aimed to reduce the impact of chance and offer a more robust estimate of the success rate. However, it is possible that more interactions could increase the probability of obtaining at least one correct solution, especially in questions whose approach requires multiple logical paths.

An additional factor concerns the evaluation process itself in Beecrowd. The platform tends to automatically reject submissions that contain basic compilation errors, vector indexing problems, or obvious memory limit violations. Although such slips can be easily corrected by a human programmer, they were counted as failures in this study, since the objective was to measure the autonomous performance of the AI, without any manual intervention to adjust the generated code. This criterion, while providing a faithful overview of the 'purity' of the ChatGPT 5.2 result, is also a limitation, as it does not explore the potential for human collaboration to refine the code, something that, in practice, many users can do by employing automatic code generation tools.

Another limitation that deserves attention is the decision to focus predominantly on the success rate when analyzing the generated solutions rather than performing an in-depth qualitative analysis. In other words, the focus was on whether the codes were accepted ('Accepted') or rejected ('Wrong Answer', 'Time Limit Exceeded', 'Memory Limit Exceeded', 'Runtime Error', etc.). Although this indicator is sufficient to assess the degree of success in solving the challenges, it does not reveal how readable or sustainable the code would be within larger projects or whether good programming practices were followed. Thus, complementary studies could examine factors such as organization, clarity, cyclomatic complexity, and efficiency of each solution more closely, thus broadening our understanding of the quality of work

produced by ChatGPT 5.2.

Despite these limitations, this study’s findings offer significant insights into the extent to which problem wording influences ChatGPT 5.2’s performance in solving mathematical problems on Beecrowd. Although these findings cannot be extrapolated to every platform or category of challenges, they highlight critical considerations for evaluating the real-world applicability of language models in competitive programming. By recognizing these obstacles, future work can address each of these aspects more systematically, deepening the investigations, and proposing strategies to mitigate the limitations identified here.

copilot, amazon codewhisperer, and chatgpt. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2304.10778*.

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